

Coagulation of Oil Field Wastewater with Chitosan

M. GANDHIRAJAN and C. S. SWAMINATHAN*

Department of Chemistry, College of Engineering, Anna University, Madras-600 025

Manuscript received 22 July 1994, revised 27 October 1995, accepted 21 December 1995

The wastewater generated from petroleum oil field during the exploratory drilling operation poses the problem of disposal due to the presence of high suspended solids, oil and grease, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD). It is reported that basic aluminium polychloride is likely to be a better coagulant than the conventional coagulants like alum, ferric chloride and ferrous sulphate in the treatment of oil field wastewater¹. Chitosan, a linear polymer containing 2000–3000 *N*-acetyl-glucosamine units², derived from the vertebrae of marine crustaceans like shrimp, lobster and crabs, has been reported to be an effective coagulant in the treatment of industrial wastewater³. In the present study chitosan has been used as coagulant in the treatment of oil field wastewater. The results reveal that the chitosan effects maximum removal of oil and grease, BOD and COD with an optimum dosage of 5.0 mg dm⁻³ at the wastewater pH value of 7.1.

Results and Discussion

The wastewater sample was collected from Adiakamangalam (Tamil Nadu) oil field during the exploratory drilling operation and analysed (Table 1). The sample was subjected to coagulation study and the plot of residual turbidity values in the treated wastewater sample against the various dosages of chitosan reveals that the maximum turbidity removal is achieved at an optimum dosage of 5.0 mg dm⁻³. Above this dose, the turbidity value again gets increased. The increase in turbidity at excessive chitosan concentration is a common effect of overloading with polymer which caused re-stabilisation of solids from the coagulated to suspended solids⁴.

The treated wastewater sample obtained after coagulation with chitosan at the optimum dosage of 5.0 mg dm⁻³ was further analysed for other parameters. The raw wastewater characteristics have been compared with the treated wastewater characteristics (Table 1). It is seen that the oil and grease in the treated wastewater is completely removed. While the BOD of the wastewater is brought down from an initial level of 84 to 35 mg dm⁻³, effecting 58.33% BOD removal, and the COD of the wastewater is reduced from 1980 to 260 mg dm⁻³ with a COD removal of 86.87%.

TABLE 1—WASTE CHARACTERISTICS*

Parameters	Raw waste	Treated waste
pH	7.1	7.1
Suspended solids	865	Nil
Total dissolved solids	143875	143880
BOD (5 days 20°)	84	35
COD	1980	260
Oil and grease	45	Nil
Chlorides (as Cl)	50985	50985
Sulphate (as SO ₄)	800	800
Sulphides (as S)	Nil	Nil
Phenolic compounds (as phenol)	Nil	Nil

*All data except pH are expressed in mg dm⁻³.

Experimental

The chitosan solution was prepared by adding chitosan (1 g) to distilled water (100 ml) and acetic acid (1 ml) and the mixture stirred for about 10 min when a thick jelly was formed. The jelly was then made upto 1000 ml stock solution with distilled water. Chitosan doses of different concentrations were prepared in the concentration range 0.3–10.0 mg dm⁻³.

Procedure : The wastewater sample (500 ml) was rapidly mixed with chitosan stock solution for 1 min and then subjected to slow mixing for a period of 15 min in a jar test apparatus. The contents were then allowed to settle for 1 h and the supernatant was analysed. The raw and treated wastewater samples were analysed by standard methods⁵.

References

1. D. S. RAMTEKE, S. R. WATE, C. A. MOGHE, A. M. SOMAN and R. SARIN, *J. Iam*, 1991, 18, 124.
2. 'Proceedings of the First International Conference on Chitin/Chitosan', Boston, 1977, p. 237.
3. W. A. BOUGH, *J. Food Sci.*, 1975, 40, 297; P. A. NADAR and M. GANDHIRAJAN, *IAWPC, Tech. Annu.*, 1984, 11, 66.
4. C. R. O'MELLA, "Coagulation and Flocculation in Physicochemical Processes for Water Quality Control", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1972, p. 61.
5. "Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater", 14th. ed., APHA, AWWA and WPCF, Washington, 1975.